

Appendix S1 for *Phylogenomics of Elongate-Bodied Springtails Reveals Independent Transitions from Aboveground to Belowground Habitats in Deep-Time*

—Detailed Materials and Methods

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Sampling, Sequencing and Genome Assembly

Twenty species were selected to represent major clades within the three main branches of Entomobryomorpha, i.e., Entomobryoidea, Isotomoidea, and Tomoceroidea, including three species of Isotomidae Schäffer, 1896, two Orchesellidae Börner, 1906, two Entomobryidae Schäffer, 1896, two Paronellidae Börner, 1906, two Oncopoduridae, and nine Tomoceridae, covering 6 out of 8 extant families except for two rarely found, oligotypic, and highly specialised littoral families Actaletidae Börner, 1902 and Coenaletidae Bellinger, 1985, which were most probably derived from epigeic ancestors in the major clades (Soto-Adames 1988; Palacios-Vargas et al. 2000). For the sampled families with subdivisions, representative species were chosen from different subfamilies to ensure a wide taxonomic coverage and to avoid to miss major lineages. For Isotomidae, all three subfamilies (sensu Potapov 2001), i.e., Isotominae Schäffer, 1896, Anurophorinae Börner, 1906, and Pachyotominae Potapov, 2001 were sampled. For members of Entomobryoidea, i.e., the closely related Orchesellidae, Paronellidae, and Entomobryidae, 6 major stem subfamilies, i.e., Orchesellinae Börner, 1906, Heteromurinae Absolon and Kseneman, 1942, Paronellinae Börner, 1906, Salininae Absolon and Kseneman, 1942, Entomobryinae Schäffer, 1896, and Lepidocyrtinae Wahlgren, 1906 were sampled. The 5 unsampled subfamilies, i.e., Nothobryinae Zhang and Deharveng, 2015, Bessoniellinae Soto-Adames, Barra, Christiansen and Jordana, 2008, Troglopedetinae Börner, 1913, Willowsiinae Yoshii and Suhardjono, 1989, and Seirinae Yosii, 1961, all definitely belong to Entomobryoidea. Except for the monotypic, extremely rare and specialised cave-dweller Bessoniellinae, these unsampled subfamilies have been proven to have close relationship with the sampled taxa based on mitogenomic (Godeiro et al. 2021) and morphological data (Zhang et al. 2019b). Therefore, since the aim of this study is not to

clarify the relationship within Entomobryoidea, the absence of these taxa will not affect our main results and conclusion. For Tomoceridae, both subfamilies, i.e., Tomocerinae Schäffer, 1896 and Lepidophorellinae Absolon, 1903, were sampled. For Oncopoduridae, representatives were chosen from two distinct lineages, i.e., *Oncopodura* and *Harlomillsia*. This sampling design is so far the most comprehensive higher-taxon sampling of Entomobryomorpha for phylogenetic purpose. Moreover, the representative species were chosen to represent a wide range of ecomorphological forms (aboveground versus belowground-dwellers) within each major branch to avoid severe bias in ancestral state reconstruction. One representative of Hypogastruridae Börner, 1906 (order Poduromorpha Börner, 1913) and Bourletiellidae Börner, 1913 (*Symphyleona* Börner, 1901) were used as outgroups based on previous phylogenomic analyses (e.g., Zhang et al. 2019; Sun et al. 2020). Species names, taxonomic ranks, raw sequencing data, and assembly accessions are provided in Appendix 2 (Table S1).

Genome assemblies for seven species were downloaded from NCBI. For the 15 newly sequenced species, a single specimen of each preserved in absolute ethanol at -20°C was processed for subsequent laboratory experiments. Genomic DNA was extracted and purified by using QIAamp DNA Micro Kits (Qiagen), and further amplified by using REPLI-g Single Cell Kits or REPLI-g UltraFast Mini Kits (Qiagen) to meet the criteria (200 ng) for sequencing library preparation. Libraries of an insert size of 350 bp were constructed and sequenced (2×150 bp) on the Illumina Novaseq 6000 platform at Berry Genomics (Beijing, China). Approximately 10 Gb raw data were produced for each species to hold the sequencing coverage above 20×, which were usually sufficient to generate enough number of

targeted loci (Zhang et al. 2019a).

We performed genome assembly using the rapid pipeline PLWS v1.0.5 (<https://github.com/xtmtd/PLWS/>, Zhang et al. 2019a): quality control and normalisation with BBTools v38.29 (Bushnell 2014), contig assembly with six rounds (k-mer value of 21–121) of Minia v3.2 (Chikhi and Rizk 2013), removal of redundant contigs with Redundans v0.13c (Pryszcz and Gabaldón 2016), scaffolding with BESST v2.2.8 (Sahlin et al. 2014), and gap filling with GapCloser v1.12 (Luo et al. 2012). The target normalisation depth was set at 20x. Contaminants were detected by using HS-BLASTN (Chen et al. 2015) and BLAST+ (i.e. `blastn`) v2.7.1 (Camacho et al. 2009) against the NCBI nt and UniVec databases. The basic statistics for genome assemblies are provided in Appendix 2 (Table S1). BUSCO assessments (see below) against the collembolan reference set ($n = 1,997$) indicated relatively high genome completeness of 66.5%–92.3% ($1,586.5 \pm 257.5$) (Appendix 4: Fig. S1).

Matrix Generation

Universal single-copy orthologues (USCOs) were extracted from genomes with BUSCO v3.0.2 (Waterhouse et al. 2018) against our custom reference gene set ($n=1,997$) designed for *Collembola* (Sun et al. 2020a). We modified the default standard deviations (σ) of the mean USCO length to 2σ to classify more USCOs as ‘complete’, because the BUSCO pipeline did not output incomplete ‘fragmented’ USCO sequences. USCO amino acid and nucleotide sequences were used for subsequent analyses. Protein sequences of each locus were aligned by using MAFFT v7.450 (Kato and Standley 2013) with the L-INS-I method. To reduce compositional heterogeneity, alignments were trimmed by using BMGE v1.12 (Criscuolo and

Gribaldo 2010) with the stringent parameters ‘-m BLOSUM90 -h 0.4’. Trimmed alignments were concatenated by using FASConCAT-g v1.04 (Kück and Longo 2014). We further excluded those alignments that violated the SRH (stationary, reversible and homogeneous) assumptions (Naser-Khdour et al. 2019) using ‘--symtest’ implemented in IQ-TREE v2.0-rc1 (Minh et al. 2020a). We generated three USCO matrices (USCO75, USCO90, USCO100) of 75%, 90% and 100% completeness, which represents the lowest ratio of taxa for all partitions. Selection of genes with strong phylogenetic signal, which can be reflected by high bootstrap supports, can reduce gene tree topological incongruence and improve resolution particularly for deep nodes (Salichos and Rokas 2013). Individual gene trees were inferred by using IQ-TREE with the ‘EX_EHO’ mixture protein model and 1,000 ultrafast bootstraps (UFBoot2, Hoang et al. 2018). For each of the three datasets generated above, we selected USCOs of average UFBoot2 values greater than 75 to generate the new matrices (In this study, we selected UFBoot2 threshold to secure high supporting value (> 70) while maintain a good number of loci (~ 50%). Because analyses based on UCE matrices often received lower UFBoot2 support than those based on USCOs, their thresholds were also set slightly lower), i.e., USCO75_abs75, USCO90_abs75, and USCO100_abs75 (Appendix 3).

Ultraconserved elements (UCEs) were also extracted from genomes by using PHYLUCE v1.6.6 (Faircloth 2016) against our custom collembolan probe set, which contained 45,815 baits targeting 1,866 loci (Sun et al. 2020a). Similar to USCO matrix generation, UCE matrices were produced as follows: aligning with MAFFT, trimming with BMGE (‘-m DNAPAM150:2’), concatenating with FASConCAT-g, filtering SRH model violations with IQ-TREE, and selecting loci of average UFBoot2 values greater than 70.

Gene trees were estimated with the GTR model ('-mset GTR'). With three levels of matrix completeness 50%, 75%, and 90%, six UCE matrices were ultimately generated for subsequent analyses: UCE50, UCE50_abs70, UCE75, UCE75_abs70, UCE90, and UCE90_abs70 (Appendix 3).

The basic statistics for the captured USCOs and UCEs, and for the 12 matrices are provided in Appendix 2 (Table S1 and S2, respectively). Ratios of missing taxa and missing sites were slightly higher in the UCE matrices than in the USCO ones. Matrices excluding loci of low phylogenetic signal had greater average locus length.

Phylogenetic Reconstruction and Topology Test

Inaccurate phylogenomic trees may stem from biological and methodological sources of systematic error (Kumar et al. 2012; Young and Gillung 2020), such as compositional bias, missing data, heterotachy (i.e., rate variation across sites and lineages, Lopez et al. 2002), rate heterogeneity, and incomplete lineage sorting (ILS). We conducted phylogenetic inference using a diverse set of analytical methods to account for these sources of bias. Measures aimed at mitigating compositional bias and missing data were implemented during matrix generation. For both the USCO amino acid and UCE nucleotide matrices, phylogenetic trees were inferred by using partitioned maximum likelihood (ML), heterotachy model, and multispecies coalescent model methods. For the partitioned ML analyses, partitioning schemes and substitution models were selected based on MODELFINDER (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) implemented in IQ-TREE by employing the relaxed hierarchical clustering algorithm '-rclusterf 10' (Lanfear et al. 2014); estimations were

restricted to a subset of models, i.e. ‘-mset LG’ for USCO amino acids, ‘-mset GTR’ for UCE nucleotides. Heterotachy ML reconstructions were performed by using the General Heterogeneous evolution On a Single Topology (GHOST, Crotty et al. 2019) model in IQ-TREE. Node supports in all ML analyses were calculated by using 1,000 SH-aLRT replicates (Guindon et al. 2010) and 1,000 UFBoot2 bootstraps. The multi-species coalescent model (MSCM) addressing ILS was run by using ASTRAL-III v5.6.1 (Zhang et al. 2018); given a set of gene trees, local branch supports were estimated from quartet frequencies (Sayyari and Mirarab 2016). Individual gene trees were obtained from the previous steps of matrix generation. We quantified genealogical concordance with the gene concordance factor (gCF) and the site concordance factor (sCF) given the reference tree and gene trees (Minh et al. 2020b) using IQ-TREE.

Modelling site-heterogeneity has been highlighted as more important than protein-wise heterotachy (partitioning) in phylogenomic analyses (Wang et al. 2019b). To mitigate long-branch attraction (LBA) artefacts, we applied site-heterogeneous models in both ML and Bayesian inference contexts. The posterior mean site frequency (PMSF, Wang et al. 2019a) model was performed for each USCO matrix by specifying a profile mixture model with ‘-m LG+C60+FO+R’ in IQ-TREE. The corresponding partitioned ML tree was treated as an initial guide tree. The resulting PMSF tree was used as a new guide tree, leading to new PMSF profile and a new tree. The PMSF tree inference process was iteratively repeated at least twice until no topological changes occurred. Bayesian inference by using PhyloBayes MPI v1.8b (Lartillot et al. 2013) was only performed for dataset USCO90_abs75 due to the computational burden. Three separate chains were run for 2,156–2,460 generations under the

CAT+GTR model (Lartillot and Philippe 2004) by using a starting tree derived from the PMSF ML analyses. The two chains converged on the same topology in all MCMC samples after removing the first 1,600 generations as the burn-in.

We tested the resultant three alternative topologies (H1, H2, H3) with the matrix USCO90_abs75 using approximately the unbiased (AU), weighted Kishino-Hasegawa (WKH), and weighted Shimodaira-Hasegawa (WSH) tests under the PMSF model '-m LG+C60+FO+R' in IQ-TREE: H1, *Oncopodura* + remaining taxa; H2, (*Oncopodura* + (*Harlomillsia* + Tomoceridae)) + remaining taxa; H3, ((*Oncopodura* + *Harlomillsia*) + Tomoceridae) + remaining taxa. The tree estimated from previous PMSF inference on matrix USCO90_abs75 was used as the guide tree and the starting tree.

Phylogeny without outgroup taxa

To test whether outgroups affected reconstructions of deep nodes in the ingroup, we performed two analyses based on the matrix USCO90_abs75 with two outgroup species excluded. First, an unrooted tree was estimated by using partitioned ML method as described above (command 'iqtree -s FcC_supermatrix.fas -p FcC_supermatrix_partition.txt -m MFP --mset LG --msub nuclear --rclusterf 10 -B 1000 --alrt 1000 -T 15'). Second, root placement was inferred by using non-reversible models (Naser-Khdour et al. 2021) when an outgroup is lacking. This analysis was carried out by using IQ-TREE v2.1.3. Confidence in the root placement was measured with both rootstrap support values and tree topology tests (command 'iqtree -s FcC_supermatrix.fas -p FcC_supermatrix_partition.txt.best_scheme.nex --model-joint NONREV -B 1000 --root-test -zb 10000 -zw -au -T 15'). Partitioning schemes

and substitution modes followed results in the first analyses. These resulting unrooted and rooted topologies were compared with those from phylogenies with the outgroup included. Relative positions between or within three superfamilies in the unrooted topology (Appendix 7, unrooted_tree.treefile) had no difference with previous analyses. A rooted tree (Appendix 7, rooted_tree.treefile) based on non-reversible models placed *Oncopodura yosiiiana* at the root, identical with the topological hypothesis H1 (see results in the main text); while low UFBoot2 node support value of 57 indicated its uncertainty. Rootstrap support for each branch is defined as the proportion of rooted bootstrap trees that have the root on that branch. Four nodes presented the rootstrap support values (Appendix 7, rootstrap.nex): 57.3 for the root *Oncopodura yosiiiana*, 25.2 for the (Isotomoidea + Entomobryoidea), 14.7 for the (*Harlomillsia* + Tomoceridae), and 1.3 for the Tomoceridae. The two largest rootstrap values indicated the majority hypotheses H1 and H2. Furthermore, topology tests (Appendix 7, root_test.csv) provided AU p-values of greater than 0.05 in three branches, i.e. branches of three greatest rootstrap values, indicating the three branches could be as the possible root. All above analyses clearly showed outgroup choice has little effect on the reconstructions of ingroup relationships.

Test for ancient introgression

Gene tree discordance may also be caused by introgression. To detect potential introgression in ancient lineages, we calculated the test statistic Δ , which estimates a deviation from the expected equal numbers of the two most frequent alternative topologies for any given branch. We followed methods of Huson et al. (2005) and Vanderpool et al.

(2020) using scripts of Cunha et al. (2021). The statistic Δ was calculated as the difference between the number of gene trees supporting the most frequent discordant topology and the second most frequent discordant topology, divided by the sum of the same two numbers. These numbers for each branch can be taken from the gene concordance factors (gCFs) analyses described above employing 1,698 gene trees in matrix USCO75. To test whether deviations from zero were significant (i.e. observed $\Delta > 0$, indicating introgression), we generated a null distribution based on 2,000 pseudo-replicate datasets by resampling 1,698 gene trees with replacement; Δ was calculated for all branches of each pseudo-replicate dataset. The resulting distribution was used to calculate Z-scores and the corresponding p-value for the observed Δ . Z-scores greater than 1.65 (i.e. $p < 0.05$) indicated a sign of introgression under the one-tailed test. We tested all 19 internal branches for which more than 5% of gene tree topologies were discordant with the species tree (PMSF tree from matrix USCO75). Obviously, all 19 branches have a maximum Z-score of 1.2828 (Table A), indicating no evidence for introgression at all internal branches.

Table A. Summary of the statistic Δ for all 19 internal branches of the PMSF tree from matrix USCO75.

Branch number	Observed Δ
23	0.7705
24	1.1700
25	0.0610
26	0.1679
27	0.0541
28	0.8549
29	0.0736
30	0.1068
31	0.7166

32	0.0875
33	0.0715
34	0.0093
35	1.2467
36	0.8720
37	1.2828
38	0.0454
39	0.8759
40	0.0109
41	0.0065

The species tree in the newick format with node/branch numbers appended are shown below:

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(Ceratophysella_communis:0.3477912783,((((((Pogonognathellus_flavescens:0.0188489839,Pogonognathellus_longicornis:0.0231627110)29:0.0449343276,(Tomocerus_persimilis:0.0360426607,((Tomocerus_nigrus:0.0174064850,Tomocerus_vulgaris:0.0173763528)32:0.0076691914,(Tomocerus_maximus:0.0154153360,Tomocerus_qinae:0.0117766356)33:0.0085744900)31:0.0138653571)30:0.0241613741)28:0.0100089055,Plutomurus_gul:0.0756789101)27:0.0628091565,Novacerus_tasmanicus:0.1071161743)26:0.0169934598,Harlomillsia_oculata:0.2725377134)25:0.0104027007,Oncopodura_yosiiiana:0.2581158111)24:0.0061413803,(((Cyphoderus_albinus:0.0781873540,Lepidocyrtus_fimetarius:0.1154597912)37:0.0056234732,(Salina_celebensis:0.1050319466,Sinella_curviseta:0.0356008853)38:0.0240850021)36:0.0112660619,(Dicranocentrus_wangi:0.0627036782,Orchesella_cincta:0.0655844631)39:0.0066682951)35:0.1482574412,((Folsomia_candida:0.1164518356,Paranurophorus_simplex:0.1834027401)41:0.0786083694,Desoria_trispinata:0.1177290074)40:0.0857466235)34:0.0474181304)23:0.0308243607,Pseudobourletiella_spinata:0.2688489489)22;
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Divergence Time Estimation

Divergence times were estimated based on amino acid sequences of USCOs by using MCMCTree in PAML v4.9j (Yang 2007). To assess the possible influence of the particular matrix for the branch lengths, we performed divergence analyses for three matrices (USCO75, USCO90_abs75 and USCO100_abs75), representing three different data size levels (683,871, 224,571, 47,887 sites, respectively, Table S2). Preferred topology estimated from previous analyses, i.e. topology inferred from PMSF, ASTRAL and Phylobayes (see discussion in main text), was selected as the input tree. To avoid to produce misspecified rate prior and unreasonable narrow posterior credibility intervals resulted by increasing number of loci (partitions) (dos Reis et al. 2014; Jin and Brown 2017), loci were merged into larger

partitions based on the partitioning schemes estimated from previous partitioned ML reconstructions. For three matrices, 1,698, 430 and 91 loci were respectively merged into 41, 20 and 9 partitions for further calculation. To reduce the computational burden, approximate likelihood calculation and ML estimation of branch lengths was performed by using ‘usedata=2 and 3’ (dos Reis and Yang 2011). We used the independent rates clock model (clock=2) and the LG substitution model (model=2, aaRatefile = lg.dat) to calculate the Hessian matrices. Because posterior time estimates were insensitive to rate prior when the Dirichlet prior is used (dos Reis et al. 2014), we set parameters of the mean substitution rate and the rate drift as ‘rgene_gamma = 2 20 1’ and ‘sigma2_gamma = 1 10 1’, respectively. Time prior for the nodes which do not have a calibration was constructed using birth-death process (‘BDparas=1 1 0.1’). The MCMC runs were repeated twice, each ran for 100,000 generations with the first 50,000 as burn-in.

Calibration point selection

The taxonomic position of the earliest fossil of Collembola, i.e. *Rhyniella praecursor* Hirst and Maulik, 1926 has been for long controversial (D’Haese 2003). The most recent published evaluation of the fossils suggests that the species belongs to the family Isotomidae (Greenslade and Whalley 1986). However, Isotomidae itself has no strict apomorphies to support (Potapov 2001). The lack of comparable fossils of Collembola and other basal Hexapods even makes it hard to determine whether *R. praecursor* is a stem or crown Collembola. Therefore, we did not use *R. praecursor* to calibrate the root of the tree. Instead, we referred to the evolutionary time frame of Hexapoda reconstructed by transcriptome-scale

phylogenomics and calibrated by 37 validated fossils across Pancrustacean (Misof et al. 2014). The study estimated the origin of Protura + Collembola at ~450 million years ago (Ma), suggesting the root of Collembola should not be set earlier than this time.

Several unequivocal entomobryomorph fossils were used to calibrate five internodes on the tree: (1) we treated the Early Permian (272–299 Ma) springtail *Permobrya mirabilis* Riek, 1976 as a crown species close to the most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of Entomobryomorpha. This fossil was originally designated to Entomobryidae (or even to the subfamily Lepidocyrtinae Wahlgren, 1906) based on the elongated fourth abdominal segment (Abd. IV). However, this original treatment omitted the fact that the elongation of Abd. IV is not a unique feature of Entomobryoidea. Notably, many species of Oncopoduridae also have Abd. IV distinctly longer than Abd. III (e.g., Abd. III : Abd. IV ratio as about 2 : 7 in *Oncopodura occidentalis* Bonet, 1931 and *Oncopodura kuramotoi* Yosii, 1964, and about 1 : 2 in *Oncopodura atoyacensis* Bonet, 1943 and *Oncopodura hyleana* Arle, 1960). Therefore, abdominal morphology by itself is not sufficient for placing *P. mirabilis* in crown Entomobryoidea. On the other hand, *P. mirabilis* shows a mixture of characters shared by extant families. For example, the presence of scales resembles that of Tomoceroidea and many groups of Entomobryoidea, the stout legs resemble those of Oncopoduridae and many groups of Isotomidae, and the annulated fourth antennal segment resembles that of Tomocerinae Schäffer, 1896, *Tibiolatras* Salmon, 1941 (Isotomoidea), and many Entomobryoidea. Accordingly, it is more appropriate to treat *P. mirabilis* as a basal crown entomobryomorph very closely related to extant taxa, suggesting this order originated around this time. To avoid overconstraining of time estimation, we extended the upper bound of the

calibration to the early Pennsylvanian when Collembola had been well present and probably diversified (323 Ma); (2) the presence of diverse anurophorins (Isotomidae) in Late Albian ambers (Sánchez-García and Engel 2016) indicates a divergence between Anurophorinae Börner, 1901 and Pachyotominae Potapov, 2001 before this time (113–100.5 Ma), and was used to calibrate the most recent common ancestor of *Folsomia candida* Willem, 1902 + *Paranurophorus simplex* Denis, 1929; (3) the Cenomanian entomobryoids *Cretacentomobrya burma* Christiansen and Nascimbene, 2006 (with cephalic bothriotracha according to the original drawing) and *Praentomobrya avita* Christiansen and Nascimbene, 2006 can be assigned to the Entomobryidae + Paronellidae clade based on the fourth abdominal segment more than twice as long as the third (synapomorphy of this clade within Entomobryoidea, Zhang et al. 2019b), suggesting this clade had originated by this time (100.5–93.5 Ma); (4), a tomocerid specimen from Campanian amber (79.0–78.2 Ma) is almost identical to the living members of Tomocerinae (Christiansen and Pike 2002), and was used to calibrate the basal node of this subfamily; (5), the presence of multiple tibiotarsal spine-like chaetae in the fossil species *Tomocerus* cf. *taeniatus* Koch and Berendt, 1854 in Baltic amber (Fig. 2 in Hädicke et al. 2013) suggests that *Tomocerus* s. l. (sensu Yu et al. 2021) had diversified before this time (47.8–41.2 Ma). The fossil information and calibration scheme are listed in Appendix 2 (Table S3).

MCMCTree result assessment

MCMCTree results (Table S7) were assessed by the convergence plot (posterior mean times from two runs) and infinite-sites plot (mean posterior times versus credibility interval

widths) produced with Microsoft Excel 2016. All points on the convergence plots fell perfectly on a straight line ($R^2=1$, Appendix 4: Fig. S2, a), indicating a good convergence for posterior distributions. Points in the infinite-sites plots (Fig. S2, b and c) showed linearity, suggesting sufficient matrix size for the estimation. Data from the two larger matrices USCO75 and USCO90_abs75 fitted a straight line better ($R^2=0.95-0.99$) than those from the smaller USCO100_abs75 ($R^2=0.88-0.90$), probably suggesting a slightly better estimation based on the two former matrices. We also generated the prior distribution of times ('usedata=0') and compared them to the posterior times. Posterior times were close to but not entirely congruent with prior times for most nodes (Fig. S2, d and e), suggesting the estimation was well informed by both prior parameters and our molecular data.

Ancestral Character State Reconstruction

To trace the evolutionary history of entomobryomorph ecomorphological groups, ACSR was performed for five ecomorphological traits most relevant for defining a specie's spatial niche: body length, number of eyes, degree of pigmentation, presence/absence of bothriotricha, and presence/absence of sticky chaetae on legs (Appendix 2: Table S4, Rusek 2007; Salmon et al. 2014; Yu et al. 2017). The well-supported PhyloBayes topology and 1000 posterior trees were used for Bayesian character state reconstructions in BayesTraits V3.0.2 (Pagel and Meade 2006). Before formal analyses, simple and complex models of evolution were compared by using a stepping stone sampler (Xie et al. 2011), with log Bayes factors greater than 2 indicating a positive evidence for the complex model (Gilks et al. 1996). For body length, a continuous trait, random walk and directional models were compared. For

multistate (i.e., discrete) traits, two strategies were employed. The first analysis used a reverse jump MCMC method on an unrestricted model to integrate over model parameters and model restrictions. The second analysis used a single-rate model by constraining all transformation rates as equal. Both analyses employed a hyper-prior approach to seed the mean and variance of the gamma prior from uniform hyper-priors both on the interval of 0 to 10. As indicated by the resultant Bayes factors, there was no positive evidence for complex models (Appendix 2: Table S8). Thus, the random walk model was selected to model body size evolution and the single-rate model was selected for multistate traits. All analyses were run for 50 million MCMC generations sampled every 5,000 generations, with the first 10 million as burn-in. Each analysis was duplicated in order to check for convergence.

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